

Embrace the Diversity of the Energy Commons!

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1. Introduction

Energy Commons can make a vital contribution to the energy transition, decarbonisation, and to combatting the climate emergency. Energy Commons are communities of citizens who jointly invest in and maintain renewable energy generators. They generate and use or sell electricity or heat from biomass, sun, water, wind, and/or other renewable sources.² Directly involving private citizens in small-scale projects, the Energy Commons contribute to a decentralised energy transition, diminish market power of established players, mobilise previously inaccessible private capital, and reduce local resistance to renewable energy projects.³

The Energy Commons are anything but a new phenomenon. In many countries in Europe, energy cooperatives ensured broad-based electrification in the 19th and 20th century.⁴ Some EU Member States, particularly Denmark, Germany, and the Netherlands, developed a tradition, with ups and downs, of stronger involvement of citizens in the energy sector.⁵ The promotion of renewable energy by governments through, for instance, feed-in tariffs,⁶ fuelled this development even further. Importantly, this development did not give rise to uniform Energy Commons. There is a big variety of Energy Commons with different characteristics and needs. To name but a few examples:⁷ there are heat cooperatives that generate heat from biomass and distribute it through their own local grid. Others generate electricity for buildings or have to rely on the public grid exclusively. Some are exclusively local, in other words place-based, and others have members from all over the country who pursue a common idealistic or financial

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² A Commons consists of a common pool resource, a community that has access to it and cares for it, and the collective action of ‘commoning’: M.R. Marella, ‘The Commons as a Legal Concept’, 28 *Law Critique* 2017, 61-86, 66 and 72.

³ See, e.g., V.J. Schwanitz, A. Wierling, H.A. Paudler, C. von Beck, S. Dufner, I. Knutsdotter Koren, T. Kraudzun, T. Marcroft, L. Mueller & J.P. Zeiß, ‘Statistical evidence for the contribution of citizen-led initiatives and projects to the energy transition in Europe’, *Scientific Reports* 2023, 13:1342.

⁴ See, e.g., L. Holstenkamp, ‘Community Energy in Germany: From Technology Pioneers to Professionalisation under Uncertainty’, in: F.H.J.M. Coenen & T. Hoppe (eds), *Renewable Energy Communities and the Low Carbon Energy Transition in Europe*, Cham: PalgraveMacMillan, 2021, pp. 119-152, p. 129.

⁵ See, e.g., T. van der Schoor & B. Scholtens, ‘Power to the People: Local Community Initiatives and the Transition to Sustainable Energy’, 43 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2015, 666-675, 667.

⁶ I. Campos, L.G. Pontes, E. Marín-González, S. Gährs, S. Hall & L. Holstenkamp, ‘Regulatory challenges and opportunities for collective renewable energy prosumers in the EU’, 138 *Energy Policy* 2020, 111212, 1-11, 6.

⁷ This list is inspired by the energy cooperatives with which the author conducted interviews.

interest. Energy commons vary in size and show different degrees of active participation. They assume different legal forms and governance structures, from simple associations to cooperatives to limited partnerships with a private limited-liability company.

Recently, the EU formally recognised the Energy Commons as ‘citizen energy communities’ under the Internal Electricity Market Directive (Art. 16 IEMD, Directive (EU) 2019/944) and ‘renewable energy communities’ under the Renewable Energy Directive (Art. 22 RED II, Directive (EU) 2018/2001). The Directives aim to remove regulatory obstacles to their access to the energy markets and to give energy communities the right to share their energy through the public grid, enabling them to use their own energy. However, as not every group of citizens is supposed to enjoy these advantages, the Directives had to delineate the beneficiaries. With the ideal of inclusive, citizen-driven, and democratic communities in mind,⁸ the Directives define citizen and renewable energy communities by setting standards for their internal organisation, specifically their purpose, membership, effective control, and the use of profits.⁹

Essentially, the Directives impose some degree of homogeneity on community initiatives in the energy sector. Where there is no prominent tradition of Energy Commons that rely upon the public grid, as is the case in, for instance, Italy,¹⁰ this will not inflict much harm. The advantages under the Directives, once transposed into national law, promise to kick-start the creation of new Energy Commons. Where there already is an immeasurable diversity, such homogeneity can exclude Energy Commons or induce a painful restructuring of Energy Commons to comply with the Directives.

Drawing on empirical research on the internal organisation of Energy Commons in Germany, this contribution points to possible conflicts between how the Energy Commons shape their internal organisation in practice and the requirements under the EU Directives. It pleads for changes to, and/or clarifications of the meaning of, the requirements in order to resolve or prevent these conflicts. This contribution first briefly sketches the methodology behind this contribution (section 2.). Subsequently, this contribution deals with the tension between the Energy Commons on the ground and selected aspects regulated by the Directives, specifically with respect to the purpose of the Energy Commons (3.), the exclusion of powerful legal persons from membership under the RED II (4.), the inclusion of low-income households in the Energy Commons (5.), the right to exit (6.), and democratic decision-making (7.). This contribution concludes with a number of policy recommendations (8.).

⁸ Recital 43, Directive (EU) 2019/944; Recital 71, Directive (EU) 2018/2001.

⁹ Art. 2, No. 11 Directive (EU) 2019/944; Art. 2, No. 16 Directive (EU) 2018/2001.

¹⁰ Campos *et al* 2020, p. 6.

2. Methodology

This contribution has a traditional legal and an empirical component. To determine the meaning of the requirements for the status of citizen or renewable energy community under the Directives, the Directives and relevant scholarly literature have been analysed. To contrast these requirements with the internal organisation of existing Energy Commons, empirical research has been undertaken. The geographical focus is Germany because it has the largest community energy sector in the EU with 1,750 citizen initiatives.¹¹ The empirical research consists of interviews, a desk review of statutes of citizen-led energy cooperatives, and the responses to a questionnaire by Energy Commons. Interviews were conducted with four citizen-led energy cooperatives, to explore their activities and organisational arrangements. A desk review was undertaken of the statutes of 570 citizen-led energy cooperatives in Germany. The statutes were statistically analysed with respect to characteristics relevant to the Directives, specifically: the purpose of the cooperative, membership requirements, requirements for an exit, voting rights in the general assembly, the appointment or dismissal of the board, decision-making powers of the different bodies, and the disbursement of profits. In addition, the cooperative's year of foundation and the statute's age were noted.

Finally, as statutes do not cover all aspects regulated by the Directives and only represent a formal reality of the internal organisation, a questionnaire was distributed and the 127 responses were statistically analysed to ascertain the application of the statutes in practice and to cover all relevant aspects. The questionnaire contained questions on the characteristics of the respondents such as the source of renewable energy, the year of foundation, the generation capacity, the number of members, legal form, and paid positions, the aspects covered by statutes, and the affiliations and residence of the members and managers.

3. The Purpose of Energy Communities

Under the Directives, both citizen and renewable energy communities must not define their primary purpose as financial profits. Rather, their primary purpose must be to provide environmental, economic, *or* social community benefits for its members or for the local area where it operates. In practice, the statutes of 21 cooperatives only feature a financial or no relevant goal at all. They will struggle to find recognition as citizen or renewable energy communities. They should revise their statute by including a relevant goal, provided their activities and the interests of their members reflect this goal.

¹¹ Caramizaru & Uihlein 2020, p. 5.

The rest has included environmental, economic, or social community benefits in their statutes. What remains problematic is that over 60% of the statutes incorporate financial goals alongside these benefits. Of the Energy Commons that filled in the questionnaire, around 72% disburse a dividend. The median of these Energy Commons disbursed around 30% of their net annual profit to their members.

These figures pose the challenge of determining whether these financial gains are the primary purpose of the Energy Commons. It is submitted that regulators should adopt a lenient approach to this issue. A stricter approach would disadvantage Energy Commons without their own grid because, unless they engage in energy sharing, the members will only directly benefit from their activities through a dividend. Also, Energy Commons generally face lower returns of investments due to their smaller size and higher transaction costs. This fact indicates that the primary motive of most members is not to make a return on their investment. Therefore, as long as the statute provides for economic, environmental, or social benefits as a purpose of the Energy Commons, it should be presumed that financial goals do not form the primary purpose of the Energy Commons. A closer investigation should only follow if there is an indication that financial gains are the primary purpose of the Energy Commons. This approach will also lower bureaucratic hurdles as the investigation will generally be limited to the statute.

4. The Exclusion of Powerful Legal Persons from Membership

When powerful companies or authorities join an Energy Commons, they may, intentionally or inadvertently, dominate the internal decision-making, thereby eroding its legitimacy as a citizen-led organisation. For this reason, the RED II precludes energy companies, large enterprises, and non-local authorities from becoming members in renewable energy communities.

This rule may exclude a significant share of existing Energy Commons from the benefits of the RED II. Eleven out of 119 respondents to the questionnaire (9.2%) reported energy companies as members, and 14 respondents (11.8%) reported large enterprises as members. If they produce electricity, these Energy Commons could still become citizen energy communities, falling back on the IEMD. In any case, they could arrange for an exit of these entities. However, the downside of this step would be that it jeopardises fruitful collaborations and exchange of knowledge and skills. In addition, access barriers for energy companies, large enterprises, and/or non-local authorities that play a prominent role in the life of members may reduce the legitimacy of the Energy Commons. It seems likely that to preserve the advantage of the collaboration, they would find a subtler way to involve these entities. The mandatory exclusion

of these entities is thus at best ineffective, and at worst harmful. It is recommended that the exclusion of these entities be scrapped from RED II.

5. Share Prices and Processing Fees as Discriminatory Access Barriers

Under the Directives, Energy Commons must be ‘open’ to qualify as an energy community. Openness means that nobody should be excluded from joining the energy community on arbitrary or discriminatory grounds.¹² The price of a share in the Energy Commons and processing fees are a common access barrier. A person’s socio-economic status and, therefore, their ability to pay for the share and the fees are widely recognised as an exclusionary or at least deterring factor.¹³ The analysis of 570 statutes of German energy cooperatives shows that the median of the minimum investment in the cooperatives equals 500 EUR, with 93 energy cooperatives asking 1,000 EUR and 43 cooperatives asking more than a 1,000 EUR. Also, this amount generally has to be paid up-front in its entirety. Only 33 out of 570 statutes (5.8%) allow for a payment in instalments.

In the heat sector, the costs of connecting new buildings to the grid may motivate such high amounts. In other cases, the interviews with German Energy Commons suggest that the administrative burden of a large number of members would be disproportionate if the minimum investment were lower. It is questionable whether this would justify the high prices of a share under the Directives. While both Directives aim to alleviate energy poverty and acknowledge the role of energy communities in this endeavour,¹⁴ Art. 22(4)(f) RED II even compels Member States to ensure “[...] the participation in the renewable energy communities is accessible to all consumers, including those in low-income or vulnerable households; [...]” This provision bans exorbitant financial barriers in renewable energy communities. It is essential that regulators clarify soon what an acceptable minimum investment and processing fee would be, taking into account the different circumstances under which the Energy Commons operate. In this way, the Energy Commons can adapt to the Directives, if necessary and/or desirable.

¹² J. Roberts, ‘What Are Energy Communities Under the EU’s Clean Energy Package?’, in: F.H.J.M. Coenen & T. Hoppe (eds), *Renewable Energy Communities and the Low Carbon Energy Transition in Europe*, Cham: PalgraveMacMillan, 2021, pp. 23-48, p. 32.

¹³ See, e.g., L. Diestelmeier, ‘The Role of Energy Communities in Facilitating Sustainable Energy Democracy’, in: R. Fleming, K. Huhta & L. Reins (eds), *Sustainable Energy Democracy and the Law*, Leiden/Boston: Brill/Nijhoff, 2021, pp. 124-143, p. 130.

¹⁴ Recitals 43 and 59-60 Directive (EU) 2019/944; Recital 67 Directive (EU) 2018/2001.

6. The Right to Exit

Both Directives require that the participation in the energy communities be voluntary.¹⁵ Voluntary participation always implies the right to non-participation. Thus, energy communities must give their members an option to leave. However, it is unclear what limitations Energy Commons may set for the right to exit. Under the 570 examined statutes of German energy cooperatives, 569 statutes subject the exit through a transfer of shares to the approval by the Board of Directors. One statute bans transfers altogether. A member may, in any case, exit by cancelling their shares. To safeguard the liquidity of the cooperative, which has to pay back the nominal value of the shares, the cancellation never has immediate effect. For instance, under German law, Section 68(2) Cooperative Act (*Genossenschaftsgesetz*) sets a minimum notice period of three months, which can be extended to 60 months. The analysis of statutes produces a median of 24 months, with 112 statutes prescribing the maximum of 60 months.

As all German energy cooperatives limit transfers and such a large percentage of them impose very long notice periods, the potential exclusionary effect of the Directives is immeasurable. It is imperative that regulators acknowledge that the right to exit may be limited and specify the boundaries to such limitations, taking into account the need to ensure the liquidity of the Energy Commons.

7. Autonomy and Effective Control as Democratic Decision-Making

Citizen and renewable energy communities must be autonomous and effectively controlled by their members. The most practical approach to these requirements is the formal approach of *Lowitzsch*. He advocates that effective control at most requires 51% of votes in an assembly of members, not on a management board.¹⁶ *Lowitzsch* defines autonomy as no individual member holding more than 33% of all votes. Effective control by members would not require a decisive voice in day-to-day business. This entails that Directives would omit to promote direct democratic decision-making and management.

The formal approach resembles the lived practice of the Energy Commons. Under the examined statutes of German energy cooperatives, the assembly of members elects the Supervisory Board that, in turn, appoints the Board of Directors. Members have little to no say in the design, implementation and operation of renewable energy projects, while the Board of Directors performs this task. The members only appoint the Directors under 102 out of 570 statutes

¹⁵ Art. 2, No. 11 and Art. 16(1)(a) Directive (EU) 2019/944; Art. 2, No. 16 Directive (EU) 2018/2001.

¹⁶ J. Lowitzsch, 'Consumer Stock Ownership Plans (CSOPs)—The Prototype Business Model for Renewable Energy Communities', *Energies* 2020, 13(1), 118, 6.

(17.9%). Only under eight statutes (1.4%) do the members co-decide on renewable energy projects.

The formal approach would become unacceptable where the members do not even have indirect influence on the composition of the Board of Directors, eroding their control. Under 14 of the 570 statutes (2.5%), representatives of a regional cooperative bank or municipal energy utilities (so-called *Stadtwerke*) must form part of the Board with decisive influence on decision-making. Just as ‘dominating influence’ by ‘controlling undertakings’ under the Works Council Directive,¹⁷ effective control should include the right to appoint more than half of the management body. Regulators should embrace the indirect democracy within many Energy Commons and clarify that it is necessary but also sufficient that the members elect more than half of their management body.

8. Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

The Energy Commons are a diverse group of communities, and their internal organisation can vary substantially. The EU Directives on energy communities offer privileges such as the right to share energy in return for the adaptation of their internal organisation. Such attempts at homogenising the Energy Commons can lead to painful transitions and disregard the need for tailor-made approaches and individual regulation. To reduce the number of painful transitions, administrative burdens, and the exclusionary effects of the Directives, policy-makers and regulators at national and EU level should adhere to the following recommendations:

- Include in the regulations a presumption that the primary purpose of an Energy Commons is not financial gain if the statute incorporates economic, environmental, or social benefits as the purpose.
- Scrap from the RED II the exclusion of energy companies, large enterprises, and non-local authorities from membership.
- Specify what minimum investment in the Energy Commons and processing fees would be acceptable in light of the need to include low-income households and whether the opportunity to pay in instalments is mandatory.
- Acknowledge that the right to exit can be subject to a notice period and define how long this period may be under various circumstances.
- Determine that for members to have effective control, it is necessary and sufficient for them to decide on more than half of the members of the management body.

¹⁷ Art. 3(2)(c) Directive 2009/38/EC.